

Теорія і методика професійної освіти

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Formation of foreign language communicative competence of students through interactive technologies in agricultural higher education institutions

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***Abstract.** The ongoing globalization process and the evolving needs of Ukrainian society have significantly influenced the training of future qualified professionals in technical institutions of higher education, particularly at DSAEU. One of the tasks of the educational system today is to prepare a competent, educated person who is willing to actively perform analytical, creative, and productive work and is motivated for self-development and self-realization. The labor market currently demands highly qualified specialists with strong professional competencies, including proficiency in foreign languages. The training process for these professionals integrates contemporary standards and qualification requirements, as well as anticipates the future needs of society. This necessitates continuous knowledge updates, the implementation of effective informational, didactic, and methodological support, and the integration of modern professional and technical literature into the learning process. Furthermore, the use of innovative technologies in practical and self-*

directed learning enhances material retention. Modern foreign language learning methodologies in higher education institutions should align with global and European educational standards while fulfilling societal expectations. The Law of Ukraine on Higher Education (01.07.2014 No. 1556-VII) mandates foreign language proficiency to facilitate student mobility and competitiveness in the job market. The most effective application of computer-assisted language learning occurs through distance and blended learning models. Studying "English for Professional Purposes" contributes to the development of essential skills for future professionals, enabling them to communicate effectively in industry-specific situations. This proficiency ensures their competitiveness, adaptability to a dynamic world, and smoother professional integration into contemporary work environments. By interacting in the classroom, students not only improve their language skills, but also develop interpersonal and group communication skills in real-life situations, creative problem-solving skills, and prepare for future interaction with society as active citizens.

Keywords: *communication skills, communicative competence, studying interactive technologies, innovative technology*

Формування іншомовної комунікативної компетентності здобувачів за допомогою інтерактивних технологій в аграрних ЗВО

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Анотація. Процес глобалізації, що триває неперпинно, та потреби українського суспільства, що стрімко розвиваються, суттєво вплинули на підготовку майбутніх кваліфікованих фахівців у технічних закладах вищої освіти, зокрема в ДДАЕУ. Одним із завдань системи освіти сьогодні є підготовка компетентної, освіченої особистості, яка готова до активної аналітичної, творчої та продуктивної роботи, мотивована до саморозвитку та самореалізації. Сьогодні ринок праці потребує висококваліфікованих спеціалістів із сильними професійними компетенціями, у тому числі володіння іноземними мовами. Процес навчання цих фахівців інтегрує сучасні стандарти та кваліфікаційні вимоги, а також передбачає майбутні потреби суспільства. Це зумовлює необхідність постійного оновлення знань, здійснення ефективного інформаційно-дидактичного та методичного забезпечення, інтеграції в навчальний процес сучасної фахової та технічної літератури. Крім того, використання інноваційних технологій у практичному та самостійному навчанні покращує запам'ятовування матеріалу. Сучасні методики вивчення іноземних мов у закладах вищої освіти повинні відповідати світовим та європейським освітнім стандартам і відповідати очікуванням суспільства. Закон України «Про вищу освіту» (від 01.07.2014 р. № 1556-VII) передбачає обов'язкове володіння іноземною мовою для сприяння студентській мобільності та конкурентоспроможності на ринку праці. Найефективніше застосування комп'ютерного навчання мови відбувається за допомогою моделей дистанційного та змішаного навчання. Вивчення «Англійської мови (за професійним спрямуванням)» сприяє розвитку основних навичок майбутніх професіоналів, дозволяючи їм ефективно спілкуватися в специфічних галузевих ситуаціях. Ця кваліфікація забезпечує їх конкурентоспроможність, здатність адаптуватися до динамічного світу та більш плавну професійну інтеграцію в сучасне робоче середовище. Взаємодіючи в аудиторії, здобувачі не лише покращують рівень володіння іноземною мовою, а й розвивають навички

міжособистісного й групового спілкування у реальних життєвих ситуаціях, креативного вирішення проблем та готуються до майбутньої взаємодії із суспільством в якості громадянина з активною життєвою позицією.

***Ключові слова:** комунікативні навички, комунікативна компетентність, вивчення інтерактивних технологій, інноваційна технологія*

Problem setting. Foreign language training for agricultural specialists has become an essential component of modern higher education. The English language curriculum in higher education emphasizes two primary objectives: first, mastering a foreign language as a communication tool that facilitates engagement in cultural and civilizational dialogues; and second, acquiring professionally oriented foreign language competence. Higher education foreign language instructors should employ contemporary teaching methods, leveraging information and communication technologies (ICTs) to enhance learning outcomes. Computer-assisted learning approaches support phonetic, lexical, and grammatical skill development while broadening students' access to educational resources, thereby enriching their academic toolkit and fostering digital literacy. One of the problems that has not been fully resolved at the moment is the active participation of applicants in practical classes - memorizing, reproducing and applying the studied material. Interactive learning in agricultural universities is learning built on the interaction of all students, including the teacher, establishing emotional contacts. The teacher's artistic, creative approach to teaching a foreign language in practical classes and the desire of applicants to obtain knowledge and skills in a variety of ways is the main principle of interactive classes.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Professionals in agricultural communication occupy a pivotal role in shaping media narratives and enhancing public comprehension of agricultural issues—an increasingly critical function in an era where mass media constitutes a principal source of information for the general population. The convergence of multiple communication channels, encompassing both traditional print media and contemporary digital platforms, further accentuates the necessity for

strategic, evidence-based communication practices aimed at facilitating informed public discourse and fostering active civic engagement within the agricultural domain. Recently, the problem of forming foreign language communicative competence as one of the key competencies for lifelong learning in higher education students is the subject of scientific interest of many Ukrainian and foreign scientists like I. Bakhov, L. Viktorova, V. Garapko, O. Zabolotna, O. Kovtun, O. Lagodynskyi, L. Morska, K. Pavelkiv, O. Petrova, R. Popov, I. Pshenichna, N. Sura, M. Shmyr, O. Yaremenko-Hasyuk, I. Luka, M. Rydell, I. Senuit.

D. Hymes and A. Halliday were among the first scholars to define communicative competence, describing it as "the ability to communicate in diverse situations, interact appropriately with others, effectively use the language system, adhere to linguistic norms, and select suitable communicative strategies" [10].

Modern Ukrainian researchers conceptualize "foreign language communicative competence" as follows:

- The knowledge, skills, and abilities required to comprehend and execute speech strategies appropriate to different communicative contexts, incorporating linguistic knowledge (styles, structures, textual coherence) and communicative performance [1, pp. 21-22].
- Proficiency in both verbal and non-verbal language use, along with adaptive linguistic skills tailored to specific speech contexts.

Scholars such as I. Berman, V. Bukhbinder, V. Korostylyov, S. Shatilov, V. Hnatkevych, Yu. Passov, G. Kitaygorodska, O. Tarnopolsky, E. Miroshnychenko, and others have explored methodologies for developing foreign language communicative competence. Meanwhile, ICT integration in foreign language instruction has been extensively analyzed by V. Bykov, O. Spirin, M. Zhaldak, and other researchers. J.M. Dewaele and L.M. Pavelescu (2021) emphasized that an effective foreign language learning process necessitates a balanced integration of traditional education methods with modern interactive approaches. This ensures active student engagement with both

peers and instructors, fostering a collaborative learning environment. Similarly, D. Djamas and V. Tinedi (2021) highlighted the importance of interactive learning methods in creating an inclusive educational space that prevents dominance by a single group or instructor.

Purpose. The main purpose of this work is to consider interactive methods and techniques for teaching English to level I students that increase motivation to learn the language and improve language as the main mechanism of communication.

The **objective** of this article is to analyze the core principles and processes involved in developing foreign language communicative competence among non-language major students in agricultural institutions. This study aims to establish the theoretical and methodological foundations for fostering a communicative culture among future agricultural professionals by creating an innovative educational environment that enhances their professional training quality.

To achieve this goal, the following **tasks** were undertaken:

1. Identifying the scientific and methodological foundations for developing professional and communicative skills during vocational training.
2. Assessing the current state of professional and communicative skill formation among students in their training process.
3. Defining the pedagogical conditions necessary for implementing effective methods for developing these competencies.

Main material. While Ukraine has made strides in modernizing its higher education system by introducing ICT-based learning models, research indicates that the development of foreign language communicative competence through ICT remains primarily confined to secondary education. There is a lack of focus on ICT-based methodologies for training future agricultural professionals in this domain. [2]

Professional foreign language communicative competence primarily entails the ability to engage in discipline-specific communication. However, traditional training

often emphasizes superficial linguistic similarities rather than an in-depth understanding of professional communication needs.

Foreign language learning motivation among first- and second-level students is closely linked to overall professional and cognitive motivation. Implementing profession-specific modifications to foreign language instruction in agricultural institutions can foster greater motivation for career growth. By aligning course content with students' existing and emerging professional interests, instructors can enhance engagement.

To enhance the professional potential of graduates in the labor market, the "Foreign Language (by Professional Orientation)" discipline must be as integral as specialized subjects. It should incorporate interdisciplinary integration, intercultural aspects, and a multi-tiered learning process. Language instruction must focus on developing students' professional competencies by ensuring mastery of speaking, listening, reading, and writing skills.[6] Language serves as a means of interpersonal communication within a multicultural and multinational context. Foreign language education in higher education should not only equip students with linguistic knowledge and practical skills but also maximize their educational and developmental potential.[8]

Successful acquisition of a foreign language largely depends on the systematic expansion of one's vocabulary, while the effectiveness of word retention is determined by the individual approach to forming associative links. A key principle lies in the creation of emotionally charged, unconventional, and often shocking, absurd, humorous, provocative, or exaggerated associations, which facilitate deeper encoding of information into memory.

Within the framework of interactive learning, several fundamental principles underpin the methodology of cooperative education. First, *positive interdependence* implies that the achievement of group objectives is contingent upon the effective performance of individual tasks by each member. Second, *individual accountability* entails the allocation of distinct responsibilities to each student, ensuring that every

participant contributes a unique component to the collective task. The third principle, *equal participation*, ensures that all learners are granted equal time to engage in discussions or to complete assigned activities. Finally, the principle of *simultaneous interaction* necessitates the active involvement of all group members in the learning process at the same time.[13, p.57]

In contemporary understanding, **mnemonics** refers to a comprehensive set of principles and techniques designed to enhance the memorization of large volumes of information through the development of additional associative connections. The term **mnemonic technique** is interpreted as the practical application of the methods defined within a specific mnemonic framework.

Mnemonic strategies typically involve two main components: first, the formation of artificial associations by replacing abstract concepts and facts with mental representations that have visual, auditory, or kinesthetic qualities; and second, the integration of new material with pre-existing knowledge stored in various types of memory to simplify the learning and recall process.[3]

Phonetically Similar Associations. This mnemonic technique involves selecting a word (or several words) from the learner's native language that closely resembles the foreign word in sound. Recalling one word instinctively triggers the recall of the other. The memorization process is enhanced by creating vivid, unusual associations – whether visual images or phrases – that make the connection more memorable. For instance, the sentence "*There is a lot of sauce in the saucepan*" aids in remembering the noun *saucepan* [ˈsɔːspən] by reinforcing the auditory similarity between *sauce* and *saucepan*. Similarly, the phonetic resemblance between *plate* [pleɪt] and the native word for "flat" (плоский) supports retention through the phrase *flat plate*. Another example involves the comparison "*a bowl is like a football*" to assist in memorizing *bowl* [bəʊl], linking its shape to something familiar. Additionally, an onomatopoeic association – such as the dripping sound "*kap-kap-kap*" – reinforces the meaning of the noun *cup* [kʌp], a container typically used for holding liquids.[7]

Rhyming. This mnemonic method involves the creation of rhythmic word pairs to facilitate vocabulary retention. For instance, the Ukrainian noun *суп* directly translates to the English *soup*, requiring no additional memorization. However, the phrase *soup spoon* [su:p spu:n], due to its rhyme and rhythmic structure, significantly aids in memorizing the noun *spoon*, as its phonetic similarity to *soup* reinforces recall. The semantic context of “eating soup with a spoon” further enhances the learning process by linking the words through a logical and experiential association.[9]

The Cicero’s Method – is classical mnemonic strategy, often referred to as the Method of Loci, the Cicero Method, or the Spatial Imagination Technique, is based on mentally placing information within a familiar physical environment. In practice, a learner visualizes themselves in a known space—such as a kitchen—and imagines attaching slips of paper with target vocabulary items onto various objects within that space. Later, the learner mentally revisits the imagined setting, retrieving each word by recalling its specific location within the scene. This spatial mapping strengthens memory through vivid mental imagery and structured visualization.[10]

The evolution of professional and communicative skill requirements necessitates a shift in instructors’ roles. Educators must facilitate increased student interest in professional communicative behaviors, equip students with communicative strategies for real-world scenarios, and leverage interactive and interdisciplinary methods.

The formation of foreign language communicative competence in agricultural students follows two primary pedagogical approaches:

1. The traditional approach, which focuses on imparting fundamental foreign language knowledge at the undergraduate level to serve as a foundation for advanced studies at the master's and Ph.D. levels.
2. The cognitive-activity approach, which emphasizes practical application by immersing students in communicative situations that enhance their industry-specific linguistic proficiency.[11]

Interactive and computer-based learning strategies, including role-playing, situational modeling, video conferencing, and digital language-learning applications, play a crucial role in fostering professional language skills.[6] The integration of innovative methodologies ensures that students develop the communicative competence required for a competitive job market.

Students reported positive experiences of teamwork during work placements, internships, or research activities, underscoring the importance of diverse perspectives in facilitating effective collaboration. The cultivation of teamwork competencies is essential, as students' resistance to group projects may often be attributed to insufficiently developed interpersonal and collaborative skills, which are fundamental to successful team dynamics. To address this issue, it is recommended that educators increase students' autonomy within the classroom environment and implement targeted training programs focused on the development of teamwork abilities. Such initiatives may enhance students' perceptions of teamwork and equip them with skills that are critical for future employment, thereby improving their preparedness for collaborative professional roles.

Interactive pedagogical approaches—particularly those incorporating simulated patient (SP) scenarios—have been shown to significantly enhance students' communication competencies and self-awareness. These methods engage students in role-playing exercises that promote active listening, empathy, and the development of rapport, all of which are vital for effective professional-patient interactions. The structured feedback provided by SPs following these sessions is especially valuable, as it enables students to recognize and address communication shortcomings, fostering a more nuanced understanding of their interpersonal strategies. Furthermore, the use of structured dialogues within these simulations encourages balanced questioning techniques, facilitating more equitable and effective exchanges during consultations. Collectively, these interactive strategies not only bolster student confidence but also

instill communication and problem-solving techniques that become second nature through repeated practice.[12]

Interactive learning methods also enhance student engagement and comprehension, as evidenced by favorable student evaluations of classroom-based interactive activities. Learners expressed a preference for extended role-play sessions with standardized patients, suggesting that such immersive experiences contribute to more meaningful learning outcomes. [3] Moreover, the expressed need for additional preparation time prior to these scenarios indicates that well-structured interactive exercises can substantially improve communication competencies relevant to professional-patient contexts. The emphasis on empathy within these exchanges further underscores the significance of interactive methodologies in developing essential communication skills among students.

The **brainstorming method** is an effective tool for enhancing the generation of innovative ideas within large groups (approximately 20–30 participants). Its primary objective is to identify multiple potential solutions to a specific problem within a limited timeframe. Brainstorming is employed as a technique to stimulate creative thinking and increase cognitive productivity in problem-solving processes. It is particularly suitable for addressing urgent tasks that require prompt resolution under time constraints. The brainstorming method can be used in various forms of activity: in work with small groups, teams, large groups ("spectator play"), individual face-to-face work.[15,P.75-79]

Effective professional communication is critical across a range of disciplines, as it enables accurate information exchange and strengthens understanding between professionals and clients. In healthcare, for example, students who engaged in professional-patient communication training demonstrated the importance of clarity, active listening, and empathy—skills that are indispensable for establishing trust and securing patient cooperation.

Conclusions and suggestions. To cultivate a high level of foreign language communicative competence among agricultural students, it is essential to implement a comprehensive system of innovative, ICT-driven, and traditional language-teaching methodologies. The integration of modern educational technologies, including interactive learning and multimedia resources, enhances engagement, enriches instructional material, and fosters independent learning. Ultimately, foreign language mastery supports students' professional development, enabling them to engage effectively in international collaborations, exchange professional expertise, and thrive in a globalized workforce.

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